

TECHNOLOGY AND MACHINE FOR TILLAGE THE SOIL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11118280>

Abstract: The advent of technology has revolutionized the agricultural sector, transforming the way farmers cultivate and harvest crops. One of the most significant innovations in this regard is the development of machines for tillage, which has greatly improved the efficiency and productivity of soil preparation. This article will delve into the role of technology and machines in tillage, exploring their benefits, types, and future prospects.

Keywords: agriculture, innovations, technology, productivity, benefits, economic ways, new methods, degradations

Introduction: The invention of the wheel some 3000 years before and the introduction of draft animals made it practical to pull something across the soil that could break up the compacted soil pan. The implement used was a plough and the invention of the plough really established the method and modes of soil cultivation up to the present era. The plough was invented in Mesopotamia around 3000 BC. It is stone age technology, where the plough was made from simple tree forks. The next development happened in about 2000 BC in China and it was the introduction of an iron share on the plough beam. It made the plough more efficient to work and is still considered as a significant advancement in the soil tillage technology. There was a time when farmers managed to till their fields using simple hand calculations and old crude tools such as tree branches or spikes. During that era, the process involved only an area which could be reached by the length of handle and also the soil in such a small area, around 150 mm, would be just pushed or scuffed. Time changed and man accordingly modified or perfected tools to facilitate easier and faster soil cultivation and soil preparation. It is the soil that gives the physical foundation and support for the plants and their root system. Soil provides anchorage and necessary elements like nitrogen, minerals, and water which are absorbed by the roots. The condition of the soil at planting time greatly influences the early growth of the crops. Failure to obtain a good stand of plants or to produce vigorous plants often can be attributed to improper seed bed preparation.

Tillage is widely employed, particularly in the traditional arable regions of the temperate zone, as a means of managing the soil environment to achieve the plant growth necessary to maximize crop yield and quality. It is vital to view

tillage not in isolation, but as the first step of an integrated crop/pasture and soil management process. While the effects of tillage on soil environment processes have been relatively well-documented, our understanding of the influence of tillage on the interaction between the plant and soil environments, both directly through effects on the plant and indirectly through effects on crop management practices, is less complete.

Whereas agriculture plays a key role in a nation's economy, tillage is known as the first crucial step in cultivation. Tillage can be defined as the mechanical manipulation of soil to provide a favorable environment for crop establishment and growth. Such operations can have profound and lasting effects on the soil environment, lasting up to thousands of years in the case of some tropical soils. These effects will depend on both the nature of the original soil and the tillage system employed. The practice of tillage is decreasing in area in many parts of the world primarily due to economic reasons, but also due to environmental concerns and new crops that do not require a fine seedbed and a restricted spectrum of weed species. Nonetheless, tillage will remain a key component of agriculture and a means of influencing the soil environment for the foreseeable future.

Importance of Tillage in Agriculture

Weeds compete with crops for water, light, and nutrients. Their presence also increases the incidence of crop disease and insect problems. However, tillage only temporarily inhibits weed problems. The soil conditions caused by tillage often encourage germination of new weed seeds. For this reason, moldboard plowing, an extremely aggressive tillage method, has been recommended as a way to "bury" a pernicious weed infestation. Although highly effective at burying weed seeds, moldboard plowing also brings many new weed seeds to the surface and changes soil conditions in a manner that often favors the growth of more noxious weed species. This plowing may have to be repeated when a new crop rotation is adopted. A better understanding of weed ecology and the development of more effective methods to control specific weeds should help reduce the reliance on aggressive tillage for weed management.

In agriculture, the primary goal of tillage is to prepare a seedbed. How the seedbed is prepared will influence the outcome of the crop. Sometimes tillage is required to improve the soil structure, while other times it is done to control weeds. In modern agriculture, excessive tillage is widely perceived as harmful, but research and application of integrated tillage methods are still essential in certain cropping systems.

Evolution of Tillage Techniques

An understanding of how present-day tillage methods and machinery have developed is important in order to appreciate how impacts on soil structure today have come about. Also, a study of the drivers and trends in the tillage industry over the last 30 years has implications for forecasting the rate of decline in soil quality in certain regions and for the development and application of new conservation tillage systems. This review describes some significant points in the evolution of soil tillage in the last century while also considering the social, economic, and political influences at the time. A second type of evolution is in the understanding of how soil tillage affects both the physical condition of soils and the growth and yield of crops. This has led to the development of new methods for assessing soil mechanical impedance and identifying critical limits for root growth. In a third type, there has been a continual quest for more sustainable farming systems through matching soil tillage methods to the needs of crops while also seeking to minimize adverse impacts on the soil and environment. This has seen a decline in primary and secondary cultivation and an increase in machines and methods that perform a combination of soil loosening and planting in a single pass.

Purpose of the Work

The realization of recent years that tillage is a biological or ecological process makes it important to consider soil tillage in the context of plant-soil relationships. Whereas soil tillage is conventionally considered as a preparation of seedbed, its primary objective can also be to create a soil condition that is favorable for the growth of a specific crop or a group of crops. In such a case, it may be necessary to manipulate soil and crop residues to affect their physical and chemical effects on soil and water. The acceptance of reduced tillage systems and the development of machinery and implements for specific conservation tillage practices reflect the changing emphasis in the perceived purposes of soil tillage.

In those systems, soil tillage is a partial or total destruction of a plant residue. The wide range of modern residue materials and the interactions of tillage forces and residue quantity, orientation, and quality are topics for interdisciplinary research and should be addressed in the context of specific machines and methods. A temporary impairment of soil structure is a classic effect of tillage and is often necessary to create a favorable environment for germination and early growth

Tillage, a crucial step in agriculture, involves breaking up and turning over the soil to prepare it for planting. Traditionally, this process was done manually using simple tools such as hoes and plows, which were time-consuming and labor-intensive. The introduction of machines for tillage has significantly reduced the physical effort required, allowing farmers to cover larger areas in a shorter period. Moreover, these machines have enabled farmers to achieve greater precision and control over the tilling process, resulting in better soil quality and higher crop yields.

There are various types of machines used for tillage, each designed to cater to specific soil types and farming requirements. For instance, tractors equipped with rotavators or rotary tillers are ideal for breaking up compacted soil and preparing it for planting. These machines use rotating blades or tines to loosen the soil, creating a smooth and even surface. On the other hand, disc harrows are used for lighter tillage operations, such as weeding and aerating the soil. Other machines like chisel plows and subsoilers are designed for deeper tillage, capable of breaking up hardpan layers and improving soil drainage.

In addition to improving soil quality, machines for tillage have also contributed significantly to increased crop yields. By allowing farmers to plant crops at the optimal time, these machines enable them to take advantage of favorable weather conditions, resulting in higher yields and better crop quality. Furthermore, the use of precision agriculture techniques, such as GPS-guided tractors and automated seeders, has enabled farmers to optimize their planting patterns and reduce waste.

Another significant benefit of machines for tillage is their ability to reduce soil erosion. Traditional tillage methods often involve intense cultivation, which can lead to soil compaction and erosion. In contrast, modern tillage machines are designed to minimize soil disturbance, preserving its natural structure and reducing the risk of erosion. This not only helps to maintain soil health but also prevents environmental degradation.

Despite the numerous benefits of machines for tillage, there are some challenges associated with their adoption. One of the primary concerns is the high upfront cost of purchasing these machines, which can be prohibitive for small-scale farmers. Additionally, the maintenance and repair of these machines require specialized skills and equipment, which can be a challenge in rural areas where access to technical expertise may be limited.

However, governments and private organizations are working to address these challenges by providing subsidies and training programs for farmers.

Furthermore, advancements in technology have led to the development of more affordable and user-friendly machines that can be easily operated by farmers with minimal technical expertise.

In conclusion, technology and machines have revolutionized the process of tillage, enabling farmers to improve soil quality, increase crop yields, and reduce soil erosion. While there are challenges associated with the adoption of these machines, governments and private organizations are working to address them. As technology continues to evolve, it is likely that machines for tillage will become even more sophisticated and efficient, further transforming the agricultural sector.

In the future, we can expect to see even more advanced machines that incorporate artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms to optimize tillage operations. These machines will be able to analyze soil conditions in real-time, adjusting their performance accordingly to achieve optimal results. Additionally, there may be a shift towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly tillage practices, such as conservation tillage or no-till farming.

In summary, technology and machines have had a profound impact on the process of tillage, transforming it from a labor-intensive manual process to a highly efficient mechanized operation. As agriculture continues to evolve, it is essential that we continue to invest in research and development to ensure that these machines remain at the forefront of innovation.

Ultimately, the successful integration of technology and machines in tillage has far-reaching implications for global food security. By increasing crop yields and improving soil quality, we can ensure that we are able to feed a growing population sustainably. As such, it is imperative that we continue to support farmers in adopting these technologies, ensuring that they have access to the tools they need to produce food efficiently and effectively.

Conclusion

In conclusion, technology and machines have played a vital role in transforming the process of tillage, enabling farmers to improve soil quality, increase crop yields, and reduce soil erosion. As we look towards the future, it is clear that these innovations will continue to shape the agricultural sector, driving growth and development in rural communities around the world.

References:

1. Aulakh MS, Grant CA (2008) Integrated nutrient management for sustainable crop production. The Haworth Press/Taylor & Francis Group, New York

2. Baldwin KR (2009) Soil quality considerations for organic farmers. The organic production publication series, Center for Environmental Farming Systems, North Carolina, State University. <http://www.cefs.ncsu.edu/resources/organicproductionguide/soilqualityfinaljan09.pdf>. Accessed 23 Feb 2013
3. Balota EL, Kanashiro M, Filho AC, Andrade DS, Dick RP (2004) Soil enzyme activities under long-term tillage and crop rotation systems in subtropical agroecosystems. *Braz J Microbiol* 35:300–306
4. Culley JLB (1993) Density and compressibility. In: Carter MR (ed) *Soil sampling and methods of analysis*, Canadian society of soil science. Lewis Publishers, Boca Raton, pp 529–539
5. Das SK, Varma A (2011) Role of enzymes in maintaining soil health. In: Shukla G, Varma A (eds) *Soil enzymology, soil biology*, vol 22. Springer, Berlin/Heidelberg
6. Evanylo G, McGuinn R (2009) Agricultural management practices and soil quality: measuring, assessing, and comparing laboratory and field test kit indicators of soil quality attributes. Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University. http://pubs.ext.vt.edu/452/452-400/452-400_pdf.pdf. Accessed 25 Feb 2013
7. Fageria NK (2009) *The use of nutrients in crop plants*. CRC Press/Taylor & Francis Group, LLC, Boca Raton, FL, USA